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**THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE PHILOSOPHICAL
ANALYSIS OF THE INTERACTION OF LANGUAGE, THOUGHT AND CULTURE IN
THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION**

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ANNOTATION

This article is devoted to the problem of theoretical and methodological aspects of the philosophical understanding of the interaction and mutual influence of language, thinking and culture in the context of modern globalization processes, which are gaining momentum, which, on the one hand, has a positive value, and on the other hand, leads to the erosion of national borders, culture and identity peoples of the world. Today, with the emergence of natural and man-made disasters, new to the world history of wars, build-up of nuclear potential, there is a threat to life itself. A new wave of globalization has invaded world culture and civilization, giving rise to both positive and negative phenomena. Thus, the positive aspects of globalization include the openness of territorial borders, mutual enrichment and transmission of cultures, joint projects, information exchange, and free trade. The elimination of spatial and geographical isolation is largely due to the development of information and communication technologies. The linguistic paradigm turn in the humanities of our time has identified the interaction of language, thinking and culture as one of the central problems. The beginning of the third millennium was marked by even more intense interest in this problem, which is objectively connected with such problems of globalization as the revival of ethnic cultures, cultural interaction and intercultural communication, and the plurality of language pictures of the world.

Key words: language, thinking, culture, globalization, mutual enrichment of cultures, positive and negative phenomena of globalization, semantics, intercultural communication.

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**ТЕОРЕТИКО-МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ФИЛОСОФСКОГО АНАЛИЗА
ВЗАИМОДЕЙСТВИЯ ЯЗЫКА, МЫШЛЕНИЯ И КУЛЬТУРЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ
ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ**

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена проблеме теоретико-методологических аспектов философского осмысления взаимодействия и взаимовлияния языка, мышления и культуры в

условиях современных глобализационных процессов, набирающих все более высокие обороты, что с одной стороны имеет положительное значение, а с другой стороны приводит к размыванию национальных границ, культуры и самобытности народов мира. Сегодня с возникновением природных и техногенных катаклизмов, новых для мировой истории войн, наращивания ядерного потенциала, возникла угроза самой жизни. Новая волна глобализации вторглась в мировую культуру и цивилизацию, порождая как позитивные, так и негативные явления. Так, позитивными аспектами глобализации можно назвать открытость территориальных границ, взаимообогащение и трансляцию культур, совместные проекты, информационный обмен, свободную торговлю. Ликвидация пространственной и географической замкнутости во многом обязана развитию информационных и коммуникационных технологий. Лингвистический парадигмальный поворот в гуманитарных науках современности в качестве одной из центральных проблем обозначил взаимодействие языка, мышления и культуры. Начало третьего тысячелетия ознаменовалось еще более пристальным интересом к этой проблеме, что объективно связано с такими проблемами глобализации, как возрождение этнических культур, культурное взаимодействие и межкультурная коммуникация, множественность языковых картин мира.

Ключевые слова: язык, мышление, культура, глобализация, взаимообогащение культур, позитивные и негативные явления глобализации, семантика, межкультурная коммуникация.

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GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA TIL, TAFAKKUR VA MADANIYATNING O‘ZARO TA’SIRINI FALSAFIY TAHLIL QILISHNING NAZARIY VA METODOLOGIK JIHATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola zamonaviy globallashuv jarayonlari sharoitida til, tafakkur va madaniyatning o‘zaro ta’siri va o‘zaro ta’sirini falsafiy tushunishning nazariy va uslubiy jihatlari muammosiga bag‘ishlangan bo‘lsa, ikkinchi tomondan, milliy chegaralar, madaniyat va madaniyatning xiralashishiga olib keladi. Bugungi kunda tabiiy va texnogen falokatlar, jahon tarixi uchun yangi bo‘lgan urushlar, yadroviy salohiyatning kuchayishi bilan hayotning o‘zi ham xavf tug‘dirdi. Globallashuvning yangi to‘lqini jahon madaniyati va sivilizatsiyasiga kirib keldi va ijobiy va salbiy hodisalarni yuzaga keltirdi. Shunday qilib, globallashuvning ijobiy tomonlari qatoriga hududiy chegaralarning ochiqligi, madaniyatlarining o‘zaro boyitishi va o‘tkazilishi, qo‘shma loyihalar, axborot almashinuvi, erkin savdo kiradi. Fazoviy va geografik izolyatsiyani bartaraf etish ko‘p jihatdan axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining rivojlanishi bilan bog‘liq. Bizning zamonamizning gumanitar fanlaridagi lingvistik paradigma burilishlari til, tafakkur va madaniyatning o‘zaro ta’sirini markaziy muammolardan biri sifatida belgilab berdi. Uchinchi ming yillikning boshlari globallashuvning etnik madaniyatlarining tiklanishi, madaniy o‘zaro ta’siri va madaniyatlararo aloqalari, dunyoning til rasmlarining ko‘pligi kabi muammolari bilan ob’ektiv bog‘liq bo‘lgan ushbu muammoga yanada qizg‘in qiziqish bilan ajralib turdi.

Tayanch so‘zlar: til, tafakkur, madaniyat, globallashuv, madaniyatlarining o‘zaro boyib borishi, globallashuvning ijobiy va salbiy hodisalari, semantika, madaniyatlararo muloqot.

Introduction

The problem of the interaction of language, thinking and culture in modern philosophical and anthropological research is of fundamental importance. Language is explicitly and implicitly connected with all spheres of culture, proving to be as multifaceted in its manifestations as culture itself.

According to the fair remark of Yu. Lotman, people live in the world of culture, they are inseparable from it, as they are inseparable from the social and ecological environment, a person is doomed to live in culture in the same way as he lives in the biosphere [Лотман Ю.М. Статьи по семиотике и типологии культуры. 1992: с. 25]. But today, with the emergence of natural and man-made disasters, new wars in world history, and the buildup of nuclear potential, a threat to life itself has arisen. Therefore, it became logical to strengthen the anthropological dominant in the 20th century with the realization that a person is not only the highest value, but also the only thinking being capable of being responsible for life on the planet.

A new wave of globalization has invaded world culture and civilization, giving rise to both positive and negative phenomena. Thus, the positive aspects of globalization include the openness of territorial borders, mutual enrichment and transmission of cultures, joint projects, information exchange, and free trade. The elimination of spatial and geographical isolation is largely due to the development of information and communication technologies (media, Internet, cellular communications), the expansion of the tourism business, economic, scientific and cultural ties. Such openness of the global cultural space expands the scope of cultural communication and provides an opportunity to conduct a constructive dialogue (recently, the term "polylogue" is more often used in the same sense) of cultures that meet the requirements of the time.

Analysis of research methods and literature on the topic

The negative aspects of globalization include the disappearance of the cultures of small peoples, the unification of education, the emergence of the so-called "Davos public" that controls the "golden billion". At the same time, some phenomena can be attributed to both positive and negative aspects, for example, migration, the spread of transnational companies around the world, and language borrowing.

The linguistic paradigm turn in the humanities of our time has identified the interaction of language, thinking and culture as one of the central problems. The beginning of the third millennium was marked by even more intense interest in this problem, which is objectively connected with such problems of globalization as the revival of ethnic cultures, cultural interaction and intercultural communication, and the multiplicity of language pictures of the world. Recently, more and more often, domestic and foreign researchers are paying attention to a sharp reduction in living languages, which leads to the curtailment of linguistic pictures of the world.

Culture, as a reflection of social reality, has found itself at the center of global changes. This can rightly be attributed to the sphere of language. For example, in the Soviet Union, the language of communication for the peoples of all republics was the Russian language, through which a polylogue of cultures took place, constructing a single language space. On the one hand, it had a positive communicative value for the relationship between people of different nationalities, since the Russian language became the language of interethnic communication. But there was another side to this process: the native language was forgotten, which led to a partial separation (in terms of language) from the roots of the native culture. At the same time, in many republics, the native language was preserved, which functioned along with Russian.

In connection with the widespread spread of bilingualism in the republics of the former USSR, a "bilingual" picture of the world was formed.

Modern processes of globalization have a significant and ambiguous impact on the formation of a new "bilingual" picture of the world. At this stage, there is an alternative language choice. Knowledge of foreign languages are dictated by time itself and becomes a condition for professional development, employment opportunities abroad, tourist trips, Internet use, familiarization with the achievements of the culture of other peoples, international marriages, migration.

In this aspect, the information and communication competence of a person should be an indispensable condition for its development and improvement at this stage of cultural development, which finds its direct manifestation in the field of thinking and language. The relevance of the topic of this study is due to the natural need to understand the role of language in the era of globalization, when a new linguistic picture of the world, a new person and a new quality of life are being formed.

Discussion and results of the study

In modern philosophical and anthropological studies, cognitive, linguistic and pragmatic problems related to the holistic analysis of signs as means of communication and the linguistic ability of a person to transmit intersubjective information come to the fore.

Questions of the relationship between language and culture have been discussed in Western Europe since the second half of the 18th century. The merit of German philosophy of the XVIII-XIX centuries was the development of the first detailed typologies of cultures and civilizations. The development of culture is perceived as a single process that takes place on a world-historical scale and is characterized by certain relationships of causes and effects, internal patterns, and periodization. The first significant step in this direction was made by I.G. Herder.

In Russia, the ideas of the interconnectedness of language and culture were considered by V.K. Trediakovsky and M.V. Lomonosov. G.G. Shpet, using the phenomenological concept of E. Husserl, founded a new approach to the problem of language and linguistic thinking. Insisting on a holistic concrete-historical and methodological approach to language in all its manifestations, he saw in semiotics ("semasiology") a kind of logic of language. His approach can be described as a synthesis of logical and historical approaches to the study of signs expressed in verbal forms. Famous Russian linguists contributed to the development of language and thinking: F.I. Buslaev, A.A. Potebnya, A.A. Shakhmatov, V.V. Vinogradov and others.

Philosophical understanding of the relationship between language and culture was undertaken in the works of A.F. Losev, Pavel Florensky. In the second half of the twentieth century, this tradition was adequately continued and developed in modern philological and cultural studies, among which the works of D.S. Likhachev, N.I. Tolstoy, V.N. Toporova, B.A. Uspensky, A.A. Zaliznyak, V.V. Ivanova.

The concept of internal duality and dialogue of culture was first formulated by M.M. Bakhtin, who saw in the chronotopicity of language a treasury of images and the inner form of the word, the mutual illumination of languages. This has found its detailed justification in the studies of S.S. Averintseva, Yu.M. Lotman, B.A. Uspensky and others. Such a perspective made it possible to see in culture the dialectical unity of the opposite polarities, which are in impulsive interaction. Yu.M. Lotman presents the text as a thinking device, refuting the established ideas about the isolation of the text and the conservation of its semantic core, and as a result, it does not "produce" new messages.

The classical problems of language and thinking served as a link between linguistics, philosophy and psychology, opening up new perspectives, including at the level of cybernetic modeling. E. Sapir notes that the world of images and meanings is an endless and constantly changing picture of objective reality, i.e. human communication. He formulated such a concept as "drift" (language drift), according to which the language moves in time along its own course. Interesting is the concept of E. Sapir, B. Whorf on the influence of language on thinking, called the theory of "linguistic relativity" (controversial in the scientific world): people are largely influenced by that particular language, which is a means of communication for a given society. K. Jung, exploring the subconscious, distinguishes between the conscious and subconscious aspects of thinking, draws attention to the role of the spoken or printed word as a sign for conveying a meaningful message and dialogue that makes sense only with mutual understanding of the interlocutors.

Under the influence of the linguo-philosophical concept of V. Humboldt (language is not a product of activity (ergon), but activity itself (energeia), expressing the "deep spirit of the people") in the 50s of the XX century, in the structural linguistics of the USA there is a direction - generative linguistics (or generative linguistics), in which the Humboldtian direction has found a new development [V.Humboldt Language and Philosophy of Culture.1985]. So, N. Chomsky, recognizing a certain degree of dependence of his linguistic theory on the ideas of Humboldt, developed a transformational analysis based on the idea of a generative model of language, introduced the concept of "linguistic competence".

Among many anthropologists, ethnographers, linguists, culturologists, whose works on the study of traditional societies, cultures and languages contributed to the formation of the idea of a multipolar human community, a special role belongs to E. Benveniste R. Benedict, F. Boas, H.G. Gadamer, L. Levy-Bruhl, K. Levy-Strauss, B. Malinovsky and a number of other researchers. Thus,

Levi-Strauss notes that "untamed thought" is a prerequisite for mutual understanding in intercultural dialogue, since understanding oneself is possible only through understanding other peoples. B. Malinovsky assigns an important place in the analysis of culture to such phenomena as language, oral and written tradition. He believes that ethical norms are based on the entire sphere of the symbolic, i.e. on the factors of verbal learning or on the acquisition of texts in natural language. The scientist attached particular importance to the linguistics of the future as the study of the language in its cultural meaning.

In the works of F. Klukhona and F. Schrodbeck, E. Hall and G. Hofstede, operational parameters are formulated to describe the influence of culture on human activity and the development of society. E. Hall introduced a distinction between high- and low-context cultures, which is manifested in the amount of information explicitly expressed in communicative communication.

Studies of the genetic factor, which largely determines intercultural differences, including the type of thinking, were undertaken in the works of Macotto Kikuhi, L.S. Vygotsky, B.C. Rotenberg and V.V. Arshavsky, F. Cassidy, I.K. Kudryavtseva, S.A. Lebedev. Psychological school L.S. Vygotsky focuses on speech activity, directly linking it with thinking (the hypothesis of the dialectical unity of thinking and speech activity). Leontiev A.A. emphasizes that the main constitutive function of human language is the function of language as a form of human thinking that promotes communication. F. Cassidy, analyzing the processes of globalization, emphasizes the technogenic, lack of spirituality of modern culture. Based on the works of M. Kikuhi, B.C. Rotenberg and V.V. Arshavsky, he, comparing the Americans and the Japanese, draws attention to the peculiarities of Western and Eastern thinking.

Attempts to describe the individual linguistic picture of a person - the carrier of linguistic consciousness were made by Yu.D. Apresyan, L.G. Babenko, Yu.N. Karaulov, V.V. Krasnykh, S.I. Dracheva, E.S. Kubryakova, V.I. Postovalova, O.G. Pocheptsov, V.N. Telia, E.F. Uryson.

Since the end of the 20th century, anthropological linguistics has been intensively developing, the search for special properties of the conceptualization of objects has been carried out, ideas have been expressed about the diversity of worldviews, their specificity has been revealed, which is reflected in the works of such scientists as A. Vezhbitskaya [Vezhbitskaya A. Language. Culture. Cognition. 1997: 416 p.], M.M. Makovsky, N.S. Novikova, N.V. Cheremisin. The merit of A. Vezhbitskaya lies in the development of the theory of metalanguage - *Lingua Mentalis* - and ethnogrammar, where the author claims that the language is focused on a specific ethnic group. M.M. Makovsky studied language within the framework of myth, where his own picture of the world is created.

The key concept of modern cognitive linguistics - linguistic conceptualization - is considered in the works of domestic and foreign scientists Yu.A. Stepanova, S.G. Ter-Minasova, R. Jackendorff and others. So, S.G. Ter-Minasova explores intercultural relations, focusing on the role of language and thinking in shaping the picture of the world [Ter-Minasova S.G. English as a global language - the salvation of mankind or linguistic fascism? 2002: S. 101-107].

A.G. Maksapetyan, exploring the languages of description and models of the world, notes that the user of this description language becomes the bearer of the corresponding model of the World and the metaphysics formulated within its framework. Kornilov O.A. substantiates the differences in the concepts of "scientific linguistic picture of the world" and "linguistic picture of the world". He emphasizes that the dichotomy "thinking - language" should be considered along with the third component - the external environment, since the language is the self-expression of national culture.

M. Heidegger and X. Ortega y Gasset note that as a result of mastering the world, urbanization and technization have changed a person's lifestyle, led to his massification, which is fraught with the disappearance of such a "gift" as "speech", "saying", "tales". M. Heidegger, calling language "the house of being", emphasizes its communicative function as the main one. The development of the concept of hermeneutics by W. Dilthey and M. Heidegger of the method of hermeneutic phenomenology as the study and comprehension of culture received a new impetus in the works of N.N. Shulgin, who considers the dialogue of cultures from the standpoint of alternative hermeneutics.

He notes that the reduction of the problem of understanding the other to self-understanding is feasible at the level of relations between different cultures.

Particular attention is paid to the contradictions between modern Western civilization, Russia, and the rest of the world by V.K. Volkov A.M. Kantor, E. Huntington, I. Shakhnarevich, Yu.V. Yakovets. So, V.K. Volkov, exploring the Slavic world and European civilization, notes that globalization threatens national cultures, including language, and the national interests of all Slavic peoples, especially small ones. A.M. Kantor proposed a synthetic approach that reveals culture through the activities of a person or a group subject. It proceeds from the understanding of civilization as interaction, communication through signs. Yu.V. Yakovets, exploring the historical cycles of civilization and the place of Russia in the civilizational process, considers the problem of understanding in the interaction of cultures [Yakovets Yu.V. Historical cycles of civilization. 1999: p. 230-261]. E. Huntington, in his writings on modern Western civilization, explores the role of language, in particular English, at this stage of globalization. Recognizing the globalization processes on our planet and experiencing concern for the fate of Western civilization, he, at the same time, recognizes the right of every culture to be itself [Huntington S. Clash of Civilizations. 2003].

The complex mutual dialectical connection of culture and civilization was considered by N.A. Berdyaev, F. Braudel, M. Weber, N.Ya. Danilevsky, I. Ilyin, A. Kroeber, K.N. Leontiev, P.A. Sorokin, B.C. Stepin, A. Toynbee, N.S. Trubetskoy, I. Shakhnarevich, O. Spengler and others [Stepin B.C., Elsukov A.N. Methods of scientific knowledge: 1974]. So, N.A. Berdyaev foresaw the path to the unity of mankind through national individualization, he emphasized the magical power of words in public life. N.S. Trubetskoy, noting that language is the main means of communication between people, saw in this process the fundamental basis for the formation of "multi-human personalities".

The problems of culture and civilization are also considered in the works of modern researchers G.A. Avanesova, D. Horowitz, V.P. Danilenko, V. Dakhina, B.S. Erasov, D. Cunningham, V.A. Kondakova, Sh. Kumona, M.N. Prosekova and a number of other researchers [Danilenko V.P. Globalist picture of the world, or globalistics, globalism, anti-globalism, globalization and anti-globalist struggle. www.rambler.ru]. They reveal national features characteristic of a particular culture, the conditions for their formation and development [Bozorov M.J., Melikova M.N. history of philosophy. USA, Primedia E-launch, Shawnee].

I. Wallerstein, J. Goldstein, N. Luhman, T. Parsons, J. Meyer, G. Therborn constitute a special cohort of world-system scientists who consider the processes of globalization and identify their impact on the economy, national cultures, communications, migration of peoples, which leads to to a change in the cultural landscape, borrowing, changes in the picture of the world.

In the field of communication and information, the works of N. Wiener, M. McLuhan, V.F. Turchin, K. Shannon, W.R. Ashby and domestic scientists A.I. Berg, A.N. Kolmogorova, A.V. Sokolov. Thus, M. McLuhan, as the fundamental ideas of his conceptual scheme, puts forward the increased role of the communication channel, which in some cases is set by the message itself. Therefore, modern means of communication no longer transmit information as much as replicate the author himself, for example, television. This gives M. McLuhan reason to consider the world as one global village, the unity of which is achieved through the media.

V.F. Turchin, exploring language as a means of communication, notes that language is included in culture as the most important component, performing the functions of the nervous system. Thus, the language is being reformatted at the level of modeling the environment.

J. Feiblman suggested using a biological and sociological analogy between organisms and societies and introduced a number of new terms, the central place among which is the concept of "implicit dominant ontology", reflecting a certain set of cultural values and knowledge inherent in a particular society in a particular period of time [Feiblman J. Movement of cultures. 2001: p. 96-117].

The study of culture involves the study of the sphere of human behavior, and an important place in this case is given to such a phenomenon as language in its oral and written traditions. As B. Malinovsky rightly noted, "all this is based on the entire sphere of the symbolic, i.e. on the factors of verbal learning or on mastering texts in natural language" [Malinovsky B. Scientific theory of culture. 1999: - S. 125]. There is no doubt that any cultural process always includes people who are in certain

relationships to each other, which means that “they are organized in a certain way and communicate with each other using speech or other symbolic means” [Malinovsky B. Scientific theory of culture. 1999: p.142], that is, with the help of language. According to V.F. Turchin, language (and thinking) is the nervous system of culture [Turchin V.F. Phenomenon of Science: A Cybernetic Approach to Evolution: 2000].

It is in the language, a sign, symbolic system, that both temporary, momentary values and ideals, as well as the basic spiritual values of the people, supporting the continuity and continuity of its cultural tradition, get their expression. But the most important feature of the language, which distinguishes it from all other sign systems, lies in its specific structural organization.

Although it is so easy and simple for us to explain ourselves in our native language that we usually speak without thinking about how we do it, the language is actually quite a complex structure. In total, there are four main structural levels of the language: phonetics, vocabulary, grammar, style, which as a whole represent a polystructural, branched, hierarchical, multi-level system of signs. The basic structural unit, a kind of "atom" of the language, is the word. As A. Mol notes, words - "atoms of thought" - are the tools of culture [Mol L. Sociodynamics of culture. 1973: p. 48], therefore the study of a language is important not only for understanding a person or ethnic group as subjects of culture, but also for understanding the whole culture as a whole. Like atoms, words have an internal structure (root, suffixes, prefixes, etc.) and are built from "elementary particles": they are sounds - phonemes (which, strictly speaking, are not signs, because they themselves have no meaning) . Atoms-words are combined into "molecules" - phrases, sentences, statements. Texts are formed from the latter - large and more or less integral "pieces" of speech, that is, in a structural sense, the text, which, according to Yu. Lotman, is a materialization of the language [Lotman Yu.M. Articles on semiotics and typology of culture. 1992: p. 25]. A person who is the only owner of linguistic competence, according to V.V. Palimova, “appears before us as a text or, better, as a word - an elementary component of the text. The ego - its structure - turns out to be semantic: linguistic ... The person himself, in essence, turns out to be a language, just as all human relationships turn out to be a language, since through the language they are revealed, in the language - the bearer of meanings - they mature [Nalimov V.V. Spontaneity of consciousness. Probabilistic theory of meanings and semantic architectonics of personality. 1989: p. 168]. Ideas about a person, therefore, can be formed on the basis of the analysis of the texts representing him. The concept of a text is a category of a real speech process, that is, a category of verbal communication that includes all aspects and features of a speech act. The text as the main unit of communication includes both content and formal categories, the definition of which follows from the rules for constructing meaning (information) and the rules for its construction, structuring (connectivity and delimitation). The grammar of a text cannot limit its subject matter to the syntax of a sentence. It can be assumed that traditional grammar as a grammar of attributive relations of units up to a complex sentence inclusive should retain its rights at this level of the structure of the language, and the grammar of the text should be formulated as a doctrine of the structure of verbal communication.

The interaction of language levels is manifested precisely in the fact that each element performs its own special private function, completed at the text level in the function of communication, which ensures communication and mutual understanding of people. As M. Heidegger notes, understanding implies, first of all, getting used to the system of meanings, the carriers of which are other people [Heidegger M. Proposition on the Foundation. 2000: p. thirteen]. If the word denotes (nomination), the sentence establishes (proposition), then the text summarizes (information). It is at the level of the text that all units merge together with their subordinate functions and are revealed in a single function, the investigator, and in the very essence of language - communication. The text essentially represents the language as a means of communication, and therefore it organically combines the epistemological and communicative characteristics of the language, i.e., such characteristics that are associated, on the one hand, with the knowledge of a certain phenomenon, expressed in the corresponding statement (proposition), on the other, - with the generalization of this information (knowledge) in the process of verbal interaction of communicants. The process of communication inevitably entails the formation of some text (for example, in its

elementary form - dialogue). The text realizes the very essence of language as a means of communication. We can say that the ontology of the language is the text, and therefore it deserves to be studied as a full-fledged unit of the language, which contains in an untransformed form all the qualities of its constituent elements in the level hierarchy (from a word, an utterance, a sentence, etc.). The task of text communication is to explore the system of language means that implement human communicative activity. The most general signs, such as informativeness, integrity (completeness) and structural organization, advance research along this path to the smallest extent. Of particular interest to researchers of culture are texts that reflect the factor of sustainability, continuity of cultural tradition.

We believe that the cultural and linguistic norm, represented by lexico-semantic classes and groups of words, should also reflect the dynamics of the development of culture, therefore it is advisable to consider it in the unity and interaction of the stable and variable elements that make up the norm.

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